

SOME POPULAR FACTORS OF GROWTH IN BANGLADESH: AN EXPERIENTIAL POST-MORTEM

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Abstract

Foreign trade (export, import), foreign direct investment (FDI) and remittances play important role in economic development and growth of a country. Over the past decades, along with foreign trade, FDI and workers' remittances have grown to become two of the largest sources of financial flows to developing countries. However, a key empirical question is whether they serve to promote long-run economic growth. The study tackles this question. The paper uses a theoretically reliable technique to investigate legitimacy of the export led growth (ELG) hypothesis for Bangladesh considering the variable import as well and also seek relation among remittances, FDI and economic growth. What we find is no long run relation exists among the variables. And there is one way causality running from export to GDP, remittance to GDP but GDP to FDI.

Keywords: Remittances, FDI, Economic growth, Granger causality, Export led growth

JEL Codes: D1, F21, C32.

REL Codes: 10G, 16E.

I. INTRODUCTION

During the most recent 10-years period, remittance flows amounted on average to about one third of export earnings, more than twice private capital flows, almost 10 times official capital flows, and more than 12 times official transfers. Remittances have even recently become as large as foreign direct investment (FDI) flows to developing countries. Remittances are an important source of foreign income for developing countries, increasing dramatically in size over recent decades. Remittances now account for more than two and a half times the global level of

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Official Development Assistance (ODA) having accounted for less than five percent of the level of ODA in 1971 (World Bank, 2011a, 2011b). A sizable number of Bangladeshi labor forces are employed abroad of which a total of 419 thousand Bangladeshi workers went abroad for employment during FY 2010-2011. The remittances of the expatriate workers stood at US\$ 11650.32 million in FY 2010-11. To secure smooth flow of remittances, the govt. has taken a range of measures which include among others establishment of Probashi Kalyan Bank, introducing arrangements for remittance through mobile phone, providing CIP facilities to the large remitters.

On the other hand, Export-led growth (ELG) is an economic development approach in which export and foreign trade in broad play a vital role in a country's economic growth and development. There has been a wide-ranging comprehensive swing towards the ELG tactic in recent years. This change has been found to be due to the actual and potential economic benefits this strategy accords to both developing and developed countries in a similar way. Export growth is said to result in augmented output, employment and consumption, all of which lead to a boost in the demand for a country's output (Jung and Marshall, 1985). Besides, a strong export sector enlarges the domestic market so that firms achieve economies of scale and thus lower unit costs. This may be likely because an export sector allows a country to trade along its lines of comparative advantage, (Tyler, 1981:127). This in the main leads to efficient resource distribution. This efficiency forces firms to implement modern know-how and bring into being quality products that congregate the demands of stylish consumers in global markets (Mayer, 1995).

Besides, trade may also help a country with positive export externality which leads economic growth (Bradford, 1994; Feder, 1983; and Sengupta and Espana, 1994). Moreover, trade may facilitate a developing country to overcome the ax-ante saving-investment gap and the ax-ante import-export gap (Chenery and Strout 1966).

These reimbursement of the ELG strategy have led, not only to the adoption of this strategy by many countries, but also to a burgeoning of many studies to test the pragmatic legitimacy of the premise (see Shan and Sun, 1998; Marin, 1992; and Islam, 1998; Ghatak, Milner and Utkulu, 1997; Ghatak and Price 1997; and Ukpolo, 1994). Nonetheless, there are still questions as to whether the ELG tactic will also be advantageous to the small resource-based economy of Bangladesh. The paper will focus this question.

Issues such as whether FDI causes economic growth and what is the causal direction between economic growth and FDI are not resolved. The same goes for export and import. There are still questions as to whether export or import causes growth or growth causes export or import. Such an important and unsolved issue deserves further investigation. This paper aims to examine the causal link between FDI and economic growth as well as export or import and economic growth in the context of South-Asian country Bangladesh. An investigation of causal link among

export, import, FDI and economic growth has strategic and policy implications for developing economics like Bangladesh.

Specifically, the objective of this paper is to assess whether export revenues and FDI can lead to noteworthy economic growth in a country like Bangladesh. To achieve this, the paper uses time series econometric analysis to test the causal relationship.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: after introducing issues in section I, section II provides literature review, while section III postulates the data. Estimation, methodology and empirical results are presented in section IV and V respectively. Finally section VI provides the summary and conclusion of the present study.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Actually the literature on the role of export as well as import two of the deterministic factors of economic growth is a very aged perception. Both Adam Smith and David Ricardo argued in favor of global trade as an important factor of economic expansion. The ELG paradigm has received a lot of attention following the highly successful East Asian export-led growth strategy during the 1970s and 1980s, and especially because of the overall breakdown of import substitution policies in most of African and Latin American countries. Authors like Balassa (1978 and 1985), Jung and Marshall (1985), Ram (1985), Chow (1987), Bahmani-Oskoe, Mohtadi and Shabsigh (1991), Bahmani-Oskoe and Alse (1993), Levin and Raut (1997), and Khalifa Al-Youssif (1997) have focused on export led hypothesis and their contribution to economic growth. There are some studies that exactly do not substantiate to the conclusions of export led hypothesis. Clarke and Kirkpatrick (1992) use pooled data for 80 developing countries from 1981-1988 to estimate the impact of trade policy reform on the economic performance and conclude that trade reform does not affect economic performance.

Regarding the FDI issue we observe that during the last two decades a huge number of studies focused on the role of FDI in stimulating economic growth in the LDC. But there is no harmony with regard to the direction of causality. Hansen and Rand (2006) found strong causal link from FDI to GDP for developing countries during 1970-2000. Bloomstrom, Lipsey and Zejan (1996) found evidence that FDI causes economic growth. However, positive contribution of FDI is conditional. De Mello (1997) found that FDI had significantly positive effect on economic growth for the countries with high income. Borensztein, Gregorio, and Lee (1998) found that FDI contributed economic growth to countries when the labor force has attained certain level of educational standard. Carkovic and Levine (2002) concluded that FDI had no impact on long term economic growth. Zhang (2001) examined 11 countries of Asia and South America and found no uniform pattern of direction with regard to FDI and economic growth. Hermesand Lensink (2003) concluded that the development of financial system was an important factor for FDI to have a

positive impact on economic growth. Caves (1996) found bidirectional relationship. FDI and economic growth are positively interdependent. Chowdhry and Mavrotas (2006) found relationship of bidirectional causality between FDI and economic growth. Kholdy and Sohrabian (2005) found no causal link between FDI and economic growth. Thus, the empirical evidence on the causal link between FDI and economic growth is varied.

There is a large and growing research literature on the economic impacts of remittances in developing countries. A number of empirical studies have looked at the impact of remittance inflows on the economic growth rates of developing countries. Chami *et al.* (2003), IMF (2005) and Barajas *et al.* (2009) find a zero or negative association between remittances and growth. Catrinescu *et al.* (2009), Jongwanich (2007) and Pradhan *et al.* (2008) find some evidence of a positive association while other studies find the impact varies according to a country's educational attainment, financial market depth and quality of institutions (Giuliano and Ruiz-Arranz, 2009; World Bank, 2006; 2008). Other studies have examined impacts of remittance inflows on known drivers of growth. Hildebrandt and McKenzie (2005), Lopez-Cordova (2006), Acosta *et al.* (2008) looked at impacts on human capital, Aggarwal *et al.* (2011) and Demirgüç-Kunt *et al.*, 2011) were concerned with impacts on financial development, Chami *et al.* (2003) and Jackman *et al.* (2009) examined impacts on investment volatility and Amuedo-Dorantes and Pozo (2004) investigated the impacts on the real exchange rate. Evidence of positive impacts from these studies is mixed. Thus, the empirical evidence on the causal link between remittance and economic growth is varied.

III. DATA

The data set is annual, spanning 1980/81 through 2012/13. The dependent variable is the annualized real GDP, and the explanatory variables are the annual real export, import, FDI and remittances as well. To test if the series are nonstationary or contain a unit root, we focus on the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) test. We have used EVIEWS 6 as statistical software package.

IV. ESTIMATION

4.1. Econometric Methodology

To construct relation among the concerned variables i.e. export, import, FDI, remittance and growth, the following equation is considered to which constant and error term are incorporated.

$$Y_t = \alpha + \beta_1 X_t + \beta_2 M_t + \beta_3 FDI_t + \beta_4 RMT_t + \varepsilon_t \quad [1]$$

Transforming all the variables into natural log forms, finally our baseline equation is as follows which is just equation [1]:

$$\ln Y_t = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 \ln X_t + \beta_2 \ln M_t + \beta_3 \ln FDI_t + \beta_4 \ln RMT_t + \varepsilon_t \quad [2]$$

The equation was estimated as an OLS regression. The estimated coefficients of the baseline equation are reported in Table 1 below:

Table 1
Regression Analysis

Dependent Variable: LNGDP
Method: Least Squares
Date: 11/01/12 Time: 19:53
Sample: 1980 2011
Included observations: 32

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>t-Statistic</i>	<i>Prob.</i>
LNX	0.253124	0.175806	-0.120116	0.9052
LNM	-0.367387	0.247448	-1.484705	0.1488
LNFDI	0.029903	0.038311	0.780542	0.4416
LNRMT	0.285719	0.098552	2.899170	0.0072
R-squared	0.589635	Mean dependent var		1.503987
Adjusted R-squared	0.545668	S.D. dependent var		0.337476
S.E. of regression	0.227473	Akaike info criterion		-0.007099
Sum squared resid	1.448835	Schwarz criterion		0.176118
Log likelihood	4.113587	Durbin-Watson stat		1.962272

4.2. Unit Autoregressive Root Tests

In order to scrutinize the stationarity properties of the data, a univariate analysis of each of the three time series (real GDP, real exports, and real imports) was carried out by testing for the presence of a unit root. Augmented Dickey Fuller $\hat{Z}$ ADF, t-tests $\hat{Z}$ Dickey and Fuller, 1979 and Phillips and Perron (1988) $Z(t\hat{\alpha})$ -tests for the individual time series.

The null hypothesis of these tests is that series are non-stationary. The ADF tests assume that the error terms are statistically independent and have a constant variance. This assumption may not be true of all the data used, and so the Phillip-Perron test is used to relax the above assumptions and permit the error disturbances to be heterogeneously distributed.

4.2.1. Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test

Said and dickey (1984) enhance the essential autoregressive unit root test to accommodate general ARMA (p, q) models with unidentified orders. Their test is known as the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test which is based on estimating the following regression:

$$y_t = \beta'D_t + \phi y_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^p \psi_j \Delta y_{t-j} + \epsilon_t \tag{3}$$

Where D_t is a vector of deterministic terms (constant, trend etc.) The ρ (lagged difference terms) and Δy_{t-j} are used to estimate the ARMA arrangement of the errors, and ρ value is set so that the error ε_t is successively uncorrelated. The error term is assumed to be homoskedastic. The degree of the deterministic terms depends on the implicit behavior of y_t under the alternative hypothesis of trend stationarity. Under the null hypothesis, y_t is $I(1)$ which implies that $\phi = 1$. The ADF t-statistic and normalized prejudice statistic are based on the least squares estimates of (4.3) and are given by

$$ADF_t = t_{\phi-1} = \frac{\phi - 1}{SE(\phi)} \quad [4]$$

$$ADF_n = \frac{T(\hat{\phi} - 1)}{1 - \hat{\psi}_1 - \dots - \hat{\psi}_p} \quad [5]$$

$$\Delta y_t = \beta' D_t + \pi y_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^p \psi_j \Delta y_{t-j} + \varepsilon_t \quad [6]$$

$\pi = \phi - 1$. Under the null hypothesis, Δy_t is $I(0)$ which implies that $\pi = 0$. The ADF t-statistic is then the usual t-statistic for testing $\pi = 0$ and the ADF normalized bias statistic is $T\hat{\pi}/(1 - \hat{\psi}_1 - \dots - \hat{\psi}_p)$. The test regression (4.4) is often used in practice because the ADF t-statistic is the usual t-statistic reported for testing the significance of the coefficient y_{t-1} . The *S + FinMetrics* function unitroot follows this convention.

4.2.2. The Phillips –Perron Test

Phillips and Perron (1988) developed a number of unit root tests that have become fashionable in the analysis of monetary time series. The Phillips-Perron (PP) unit root tests vary from the ADF tests largely in how they deal with sequential correlation and heteroskedasticity in the errors. In particular, where the ADF tests use a parametric autoregression to estimate the ARMA arrangement of the errors in the test regression, the PP tests disregard any sequential correlation in the test regression. The test regression for the PP tests is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta y_t &= \beta' D_t + \pi y_{t-1} + u_t \\ u_t &\approx I(0) \end{aligned} \quad [7]$$

Where u_t is $I(0)$ and may be heteroskedastic. The PP tests correct for any sequential (or serial) correlation and heteroskedasticity in the errors u_t of the test regression by directly modifying the test statistics $t_{\pi=0}$ and $T\hat{\pi}$. These modified statistics, denoted Z_t and Z_π are given by

$$Z_t = \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}^2}{\hat{\lambda}^2}\right)^{1/2} \cdot t_{\pi=0} - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\hat{\lambda}^2 - \hat{\sigma}^2}{\hat{\lambda}^2}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{T \cdot SE(\hat{\pi})}{\hat{\sigma}^2}\right)$$

$$Z_\pi = T\hat{\pi} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{T^2 \cdot SE(\hat{\pi})}{\hat{\sigma}^2} (\hat{\lambda}^2 - \hat{\sigma}^2)$$

The terms $\hat{\sigma}^2$ and $\hat{\lambda}^2$ are consistent estimates of the variance parameters.

Under the null hypothesis that $\pi = 0 = 0$, the PP Z_t and Z_π statistics have the same asymptotic distributions as the ADF t-statistic and normalized bias statistics. One improvement of the PP tests over the ADF tests is that the PP tests are vigorous to broad forms of heteroskedasticity in the error term u_t . Another advantage is that the user does not have to identify a lag length for the test regression.

The result of the unit root test is displayed at table 2 and 3 respectively.

Table 2
Unit root test (Non- Stationary)

Variables	Lag	ADF At Level		PP At Level		Decision
		Intercept	Trend & Intercept	Intercept	Trend & Intercept	Order of Integration
LnGDP	1	-1.987	-4.317*	3.990***	-6.896***	I(0)
LnX	1	-0.80	-2.835	-0.296	-4.943***	I(0)
LnM	1	0.331	-2.199	0.151	-3.362**	I(0)
LnFDI	1	-0.807	-3.502**	-0.782	-3.476**	I(0)
LnRMT	1	1.194	-0.875	0.162	-1.572	I(0)

Notes: 1) *denotes significance level at 5% and 10%; **denotes significance level at 10% While***denotes significance level at 1%, 5% and 10%.

2) The test statistics value of PP test is based on Spectral estimation method-Bartlett Kernel and the Bandwidth is New-West Bandwidth automatic selection by the software itself.

Table 3
Unit root test (stationary)

Variables	Lag	ADF		PP		Decision
		At First Difference		At First Difference		Order of Integration
		Intercept	Trend & Intercept	Intercept	Trend & Intercept	
LnGDP	1	-7.343***	-7.302***	-3.990***	-10.377***	I(1)
LnX	1	-6.547***	-6.425***	-0.296*	-11.457***	I(1)
LnM	1	-0.883***	-4.463**	-11.665***	-7.031***	I(1)
LnFDI	1	-5.341**	-5.362***	-6.805***	-6.753***	I(1)
LnRMT	1	-4.136***	-4.572***	-6.638***	-7.646***	I(1)

Notes: 1) *denotes significance level at 5% and 10%; **denotes significance level at 10% While***denotes significance level at 1%, 5% and 10%.

2) The test statistics value of PP test is based on Spectral estimation method-Bartlett Kernel and the Bandwidth is New-West Bandwidth automatic selection by the software itself.

4.3. Cointegration Test

Johansen Full-Information Maximum Likelihood Method

Although Engle-Granger (1987) first proposed cointegration techniques, there are some shortcomings in their methodology. First, Engle-Granger method gives deliberate choice of the endogenous variable to put on the left-hand side of the model. They also ignore the possibility of more than one cointegrating vector when more than two variables are included in the model. On the contrary, in the Johansen multivariate approach, all the variables are explicitly endogenous so that no arbitrary normalization has to be made without testing. Thus, the study also employed the Johansen cointegration test technique using Trace Statistic and Maximum Eigen value statistic.

The time series variables of our model (equation 2) for investigating the effect on growth, incorporated in this paper, is considered to follow the first order Vector Auto Regressive (VAR) representation defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \ln Y_{i,t} &= \Pi_{11} \ln Y_{i,t-1} + \Pi_{12} \ln X_{i,t-1} + \Pi_{13} \ln M_{i,t-1} + \Pi_{14} \ln FDI_{i,t-1} + \Pi_{15} \ln RMT_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon_{\ln Y_{i,t}} \\ \ln X_{i,t} &= \Pi_{21} \ln Y_{i,t-1} + \Pi_{22} \ln X_{i,t-1} + \Pi_{23} \ln M_{i,t-1} + \Pi_{24} \ln FDI_{i,t-1} + \Pi_{25} \ln RMT_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon_{\ln X_{i,t}} \\ \ln M_{i,t} &= \Pi_{31} \ln Y_{i,t-1} + \Pi_{32} \ln X_{i,t-1} + \Pi_{33} \ln M_{i,t-1} + \Pi_{34} \ln FDI_{i,t-1} + \Pi_{35} \ln RMT_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon_{\ln M_{i,t}} \quad [8] \\ \ln FDI_{i,t} &= \Pi_{41} \ln Y_{i,t-1} + \Pi_{42} \ln X_{i,t-1} + \Pi_{43} \ln M_{i,t-1} + \Pi_{44} \ln FDI_{i,t-1} + \Pi_{45} \ln RMT_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon_{\ln FDI_{i,t}} \\ \ln RMT_{i,t} &= \Pi_{51} \ln Y_{i,t-1} + \Pi_{52} \ln X_{i,t-1} + \Pi_{53} \ln M_{i,t-1} + \Pi_{54} \ln FDI_{i,t-1} + \Pi_{55} \ln RMT_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon_{\ln RMT_{i,t}} \end{aligned}$$

Now, subtracting lagged dependent variables from equations [8], the following matrix notation can be constructed:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta \ln Y_{i,t} \\ \Delta \ln X_{i,t} \\ \Delta \ln M_{i,t} \\ \Delta \ln FDI_{i,t} \\ \Delta \ln RMT_{i,t} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \Gamma_{11} & \Gamma_{12} & \Gamma_{13} & \Gamma_{14} & \Gamma_{15} \\ \Gamma_{21} & \Gamma_{22} & \Gamma_{23} & \Gamma_{24} & \Gamma_{25} \\ \Gamma_{31} & \Gamma_{32} & \Gamma_{33} & \Gamma_{34} & \Gamma_{35} \\ \Gamma_{41} & \Gamma_{42} & \Gamma_{43} & \Gamma_{44} & \Gamma_{45} \\ \Gamma_{51} & \Gamma_{52} & \Gamma_{53} & \Gamma_{54} & \Gamma_{55} \end{pmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \ln Y_{i,t} \\ \ln X_{i,t} \\ \ln M_{i,t} \\ \ln FDI_{i,t} \\ \ln RMT_{i,t} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{\ln Y_{i,t}} \\ \varepsilon_{\ln X_{i,t}} \\ \varepsilon_{\ln M_{i,t}} \\ \varepsilon_{\ln FDI_{i,t}} \\ \varepsilon_{\ln RMT_{i,t}} \end{bmatrix} \quad [9]$$

Where $\Gamma_{11} = \Pi_{11} - 1$, $\Gamma_{22} = \Pi_{22} - 1$, $\Gamma_{33} = \Pi_{33} - 1$, $\Gamma_{44} = \Pi_{44} - 1$, $\Gamma_{55} = \Pi_{55} - 1$, $\Gamma_{12} = \Pi_{12}$, $\Gamma_{13} = \Pi_{13}$, $\Gamma_{21} = \Pi_{21}$, $\Gamma_{23} = \Pi_{23}$, $\Gamma_{31} = \Pi_{31}$, $\Gamma_{32} = \Pi_{32}$, $\Gamma_{14} = \Pi_{14}$, $\Gamma_{24} = \Pi_{24}$, $\Gamma_{34} = \Pi_{34}$, $\Gamma_{44} = \Pi_{44}$, $\Gamma_{51} = \Pi_{51}$, $\Gamma_{52} = \Pi_{52}$, $\Gamma_{53} = \Pi_{53}$, $\Gamma_{54} = \Pi_{54}$ and $\ln Y_{it}$, $\ln X_{it}$, $\ln M_{it}$, $\ln FDI_{it}$ and $\ln RMT_{it}$ are integrated of order one i.e., $I(1)$. Johansen recommends two different likelihood ratio tests of the significance of the canonical correlations and thereby the reduced rank of the matrix: the trace test and maximum eigen value test i.e.

$$\lambda_{trace(r)} = -T \sum_{i=r+1}^k \ln(1 - \hat{\lambda}_i)$$

$$\lambda_{\max(r,r+1)} = -T \ln(1 - \hat{\lambda}_{r+1})$$

Here T is the sample size and $\hat{\lambda}$ is the i^{th} largest canonical association. The trace tests the null hypothesis of r cointegrating vectors against the alternative hypothesis of n cointegrating vectors. The maximum eigenvalue test, in contrast, tests the null hypothesis of r cointegrating vectors against the alternative hypothesis of $r+1$ cointegrating vectors. Asymptotic critical values can be got from Johansen and Juselius (1990).

The result of the Johansen Juselius test is displayed at table 4:

Table 4
Johansen Juselius test

Trend: constant; Number of observation = 30
Sample: 1982 – 2011; Lags = 2
vecrank lngdp lnX lnM lnFDI lnRMT, trend(constant) max levela

JOHANSEN AND JUSELIUS COINTEGRATION RESULT

<i>Hypothesis</i>	$\lambda_{\max}$					λ_{trace}				
Null	r = 0	r ≤ 1	r ≤ 2	r ≤ 3	r ≤ 4	r = 0	r ≤ 1	r ≤ 2	r ≤ 3	r ≤ 4
Alternative	r = 1	r = 2	r = 3	r = 4	r = 5	r = 1	r = 2	r = 3	r = 4	r = 5
5% critical value	23.864 (33.46)	17.217 (27.07)	14.866 (20.97)	7.5102 (14.07)	0.2077 (3.76)	63.666* (68.52)	39.8014* (47.21)	22.5841* (29.68)	7.7180 (15.41)	0.2077 (3.76)
1% critical value	(38.77)	(32.24)	(25.52)	(12.09)	6.65	(76.07)	(54.46)	(35.65)	(20.04)	(6.65)

Notes: (i) r = number of cointegrating vectors; (ii) The lag order for each VAR is chosen by AIC as shown in parenthesis; (iii) * denote acceptance of the null hypothesis at the 5% and 1% significance level respectively meaning no cointegration i.e. no long run relation. (iii) The numbers in bold format are the calculated value of λ -Max statistics ($\lambda_{\max}$) and Trace statistics (λ_{trace}) respectively.

Table 4 above reports Johansen–Juselius Cointegration results. Both the ‘trace statistic’ and ‘eigen value test’ leads to the acceptance of the null hypothesis of $r = 0$ (no cointegrating vectors) against the alternative hypothesis $r > 0$ (one or more cointegrating vectors), the null of $r \leq 1$ against the alternative of $r > 2$ (two or more cointegrating vectors) while the null of $r \leq 2$ against the alternative of $r = 3$ (three or more cointegrating vectors), the null of $r \leq 3$ against $r = 4$ and the null of $r \leq 4$ against $r = 5$. Both the trace statistics and max statistics jointly reject the alternative hypothesis and accept the null of no cointegratoiin. Thus the results provide evidence of no cointegrating relationship among the variables in our model.

4.4. Granger Causality Test

As mentioned earlier, the present study has adopted the Granger Causality Test to test the short-run nature and the direction of causality among annual real GDP, annual export, import, FDI and remittance in Bangladesh. The following pair wise Granger Causality model is estimated:

Causality between GDP and Export:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Y_t &= \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^l \alpha_i Y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^l \beta_i X_{t-i} + u_t \\
 X_t &= \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^l \alpha_i X_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^l \beta_i Y_{t-i} + v_t
 \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

Causality between GDP and Import:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Y_t &= \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^l \alpha_i Y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^l \delta_i M_{t-i} + u_t \\
 M_t &= \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^l \alpha_i M_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^l \beta_i Y_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t
 \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

Causality between FDI and GDP:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Y_t &= \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^l \alpha_i Y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^l \beta_i FDI_{t-i} + u_t \\
 FDI_t &= \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^l \alpha_i FDI_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^l \beta_i Y_{t-i} + v_t
 \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

Causality between remittance and GDP:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Y_t &= \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^l \alpha_i Y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^l \beta_i RMT_{t-i} + u_t \\
 RMT_t &= \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^l \alpha_i RMT_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^l \beta_i Y_{t-i} + v_t
 \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

The number of lagged terms to be introduced in the Granger Causality Test is an important practical question in the analysis. In the present study the above models were estimated up to four lags to see the changes or variations in the results (if any). However, except a little bit no considerable changes and variations in the estimated different lag models were found. The results of pair wise Granger Causality Test conducted between GDP v/s Export (equation 10), GDP v/s Import (equation 11), GDP v/s FDI (equation 12) and GDP v/s remittances (equation 13) is reported in Table 5.

V. EMPIRICAL RESULTS

Table 1 shows regression analysis of the considered variables. The coefficient on export is positively correlated with the growth rate. A one-percentage point increase

in export is associated with a 0.2531 percentage point increase in growth. Import variable has negative sign. A one-percentage point increase of import is associated with a 0.3673 percentage point decrease in growth. That is import tends to affect our growth negatively. It has negative contribution on growth. And surprisingly we see FDI has very little contribution on growth. A one-percentage point increase in FDI leads to 0.0299 percentage point increase in growth. Remittances seem to be more helpful for our economy than to export. A one-percentage point increase in remittance is associated with a 0.2857 percentage point increase in growth. Finally, R-Sq and R-Sq (adj) both show expected values.

Tables 2 and 3 show the result of unit root test. Table 3 confirms that all the variables are stationary in the first differenced series i.e., $I(1)$ in all the cases. The results provide the basis for the test of long run relationship among the variables.

Johansen–Juselius Cointegration results reported in table 4 states that both the ‘trace statistic’ and ‘eigen value test’ leads to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. Thus the results provide evidence of no cointegrating relationship among the variables in our model.

Table 5 shows Pair wise Granger Causality Tests of the variables. At first stage (equation 10) we have done the causality between GDP and export. Up to two lags, there is feedback or bilateral causality between GDP and export. However starting from lags three to lag four we get the same result that export causes GDP but GDP does not Granger causes export. Actually in all cases we see that export causes GDP. So our conclusion is export Granger causes GDP but GDP does not. And at second stage (equation 11) we have done the causality between GDP and import. At first lags there is feedback relation between GDP and import. But just after that up to lags four both GDP and import are independent from each other i.e. no statistical visible relation exists. At third stage (equation 12) causality between GDP and FDI is shown. There is bilateral relation between GDP and FDI at lags one. At lags two we see GDP Granger causes FDI but FDI does not causes GDP. After that we get the same result up to lags four i.e. GDP Granger causes FDI but not that FDI causes GDP. So finally our conclusion is GDP causes FDI and FDI does not cause GDP. At final stage we have shown the causality between GDP and remittances. Though there is feedback relation between GDP and remittance at lags one but after that we get the same output that remittance Granger causes GDP but GDP does not Granger causes remittance.

VI. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

In the theoretical literature that has evolved during the last three decades, there has been greater focus on the critical role of export and import as important vehicle to speed up economic growth. Most economists have argued that opening up of economies is an effective strategy of achieving faster economic growth. It is asserted that export growth emanating from outward oriented economic policies leads to boost GDP growth. Also, there is potential for reverse causality, i.e. GDP growth

leads to export growth. These issues are still debatable, and there is contradictory empirical evidence which rejects the hypothesis of such relationships between economic and export growth. Through the cointegration test we see that there exists no long run relation among the variables. The result of causality test suggests one way causality running from export to GDP. So what we think is that promoting exports via export promotion policies will contribute to economic growth in Bangladesh. On the other hand, the results of the paper also suggest that we should ponder the cost of policies aimed at improving local conditions versus those that seek to attract FDI. Better local conditions not only draw foreign companies but also let host economies to maximize the benefits of foreign investments. Since we have already seen by the causality test that causal link runs from economic growth to FDI. If the causal link runs from economic growth to FDI, it means that economic growth is a prerequisite for attracting and captivating FDI. In such a case, the policy implication is that Bangladesh must lay emphasis on economic growth rather than going after FDI. Finally as the largest source of foreign capital, worker remittance act as a boon to the economy. They affect economic growth positively and become an important component of the BOP. A policy implication which may be drawn from this study is that Bangladesh can improve their economic growth, not only by investing on the traditional sources of growth such as investment in physical and human capital, trade, and foreign direct investment, but also by strategically harnessing the contributions of remittances by ensuring their efficient transfers and reducing the cost of transfers by improving their governance performance.

References

- Acosta, P., C. Calderon, P. Fajnzylber, and H. Lopez (2008), What is the impact of international remittances on poverty and inequality in Latin America?, *World Development*, Vol.36, No.1, pp.89-114.
- Aggarwal, R., A. Demirgüç-Kunt, and M.S. Martinez Peria (2011) Do remittances promote financial development, *Journal of Development Economics*, Vol. 96, pp. 255-264.
- Amuedo-Dorantes, C. and S. Pozo (2004), Workers' remittances and the real exchange rate: A paradox of gifts, *World Development*, Vol.32, No.8, pp.1407-1417.
- Bahmani-Oskoe, M and J. Alse (1993), "Export Growth and Economic Growth: An Application of Cointegration and Error-Correction Modelling", *Journal of Development Areas*, Vol. 27: 535-542.
- Bahmani-Oskoe, M.; H. Mohtadi and G. Shabsigh (1991) "Exports, Growth and Causality in LDCs: A Re-examination" *Journal of Development Economics*, Vol. 36: 405-415.
- Balassa, B. (1978), "Exports and Economic Growth: Further Evidence" *Journal of Development Economics*, Vol. 5: 181-189.
- Balassa, B. (1985), "Exports Policy Choices and Economic Growth in Developing Countries after the 1973 Oil Shocks" *Journal of Development Economics*, Vol. 18: 23-35.
- Balassa, Bela. (1984), Exports, Policy choices and Economic Growth in Developing Countries After the 1973 Oil Shock, *World development*.
- Blomstrom, M., "Foreign Investment and Productivity Efficiency: The Case of Mexico", *Journal of Industrial Economics* 15, 1986, pp. 97-110.

- Blomstrom, M., R.E. Lipsey and M. Zejan. (1994), "What Explains Developing Country Growth", NBER Working paper No. 4132 (Cambridge, MA: NBER).
- Borensztein, E. J., De Gregorio, and J.W.Lee. (1998), "How Does Foreign Direct Investment After Economic Growth", *Journal of International Economics*, 34 (1), 115-135.
- Bradford, C. I. (1994), *From Trade-Driven Growth to Growth-Driven Trade: Reappraising the East Asian Development Experience*. Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development.
- Carkovic, M. and R. Levine. (2002), "Does Foreign Direct Investment Accelerate Economic Growth?", Working Paper (University of Minnesota Department of Finance, available at: www//ssrn.com/abstract=314924)
- Catrinescu, N., M. Leon-Ledesma, M. Piracha, and B. Quillin (2009) Remittances, institutions, and economic growth, *World Development*, Vol.37, No.1, pp.81-92.
- Chami, R., C. Fullenkamp, and S. Jahjah (2003), Are immigrant remittance flows a source of capital for development?, IMF Working Paper WP/03/189. International Monetary Fund: Washington.
- Chenery, H., B., Strout, A. M., "Foreign Assistance and Economic Development", *The American Economic Review*, Volume LVI, Number 4, Part I, September 1966.
- Chow, P.C.Y. (1987), Causality between Export Growth and Industrial Development: Empirical Evidence from Newly Industrialised Countries, *Journal of Development Economics*, 28(1), pp. 265-276.
- Chowdhry, A. and G. Mavrotas. (2006), "FDI and Growth: What Causes What", *The World Economy*, 29 (1), 42-58.
- Clarke, R. and C. Kirkpatrick (1992), "Trade Policy Reform and Economic Performance in Developing Countries: Assessing the Empirical Evidence, in R. Adhikari, C. K Kirkpatrick and J. Weiss (eds), *Industrial and Trade Policy Reform in Developing Countries*, Manchester: Manchester University Press.
- De Mello, L.R. (1997), Foreign Direct Investment in Developing Countries and Growth: A Selective Survey", *Journal of Development Studies*, 34 (1), 1-34.
- Edwards, S., "Trade Orientation, Distortion and Growth in Developing Countries", *Journal of Development Economics*, 39, 1992, pp. 31-57.
- Engle, R. E. and Granger, C. W. J. (1987), Cointegration and error-correction: representation, estimation, and testing, *Econometrica*, 55, 251-76.
- Feder, Gershon, (1983), On Exports and Economic Growth. *Journal of Development Economics* 12: 59-73.
- Ghatak, S. and S. W. Price. (1997), Export Composition and Economic Growth: Cointegration and Causality Evidence for India. *Weltwirtschaftliches Archiv* 133(3):538-553.
- Ghatak, S., C. Milner and U. Utkulu, (1997), Exports, Export Composition and Growth: cointegration and Causality Evidence for Malaysia. *Applied Economic* 29: 213-223.
- Giuliano, P. and M. Ruiz-Arranz (2009), Remittances, financial development, and growth, *Journal of Development Economics*, Vol.90, No.1, pp.144-152.
- Hansen, Henrick and John Rand. (2006), "On the Causal Links Between FDI and Growth in Developing Countries", *The World Economy*, 29 (1), 21-41.
- Helpman, E., Krugman, P.R. (1985), *Market Structure and Foreign Trade*. Cambridge: MIT Press.
- Hermes, Niels and Robert Lensink. (2003), "Foreign Direct Investment, Financial Development and Economic Growth", *Journal of Development Studies*, 40 (1), 142-163.

- Irwin, Douglas A., "Did Import Substitution Promote Growth in the Late Nineteenth Century?", *NBER Working Paper No. W8751*, February, 2002.
- Islam, M. N. (1998), Export Expansion and Economic Growth: testing for cointegration and causality. *Applied Economics* 30: 415-425.
- Jayanthakumaran, K. "Industrialisation: Import Substitution to Export Promotion", University of Wollongong, Department of Economics, *Working Paper Series*, No 00-09, 2000, available at <http://www.uow.edu.au/content/groups/public/@web/@commerce/@econ/documents/doc/uow012101.pdf>
- Jongwanich, J. (2007), Workers' remittances, economic growth and poverty in developing Asia and the Pacific countries, UNESCAP Working Paper WP/07/01, Bangkok: ESCAP.
- Jung, W.S. and P.J. Marshall (1985), "Exports, Growth and Causality in Developing Countries" *Journal of Development Economics*, Vol. 18: 1-12.
- Jung, Woo. S. and P. J. Marshall, (1985), Exports, Growth and Causality in Development Countries. *Journal of Development Economics* 18: 1-12.
- Khalifa Al-Youssif Y. (1997), "Exports and Growth: Some Empirical Evidence from the Arab Gulf States" *Applied Economics*, Vol. 29: 693-697.
- Kholdy, Shady and Ahmad Sohrabian (2005), "Financial Markets, FDI, and Economic Growth: Granger Causality Tests in Panel Data Model", EFA 2005 Moscow Meetings.
- Levin, A. and L.K. Raut (1997), "Complementarities between Exports and Human Capital: Evidence from the Semi-Industrialized Countries" *Economic Development and Cultural Change*, Vol. 46: 155-174.
- Marin, Dalia. (1992), Is the Export-Led Growth Valid for Developed Countries? *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 678-688.
- Mayer, Jorg. (1996), Learning Sequences and Structural Diversification in Developing Countries. *Journal of Development Studies* 33:210-299.
- Pradhan, G., M. Upadhyay, and K. Upadhyaya (2008), Remittances and economic growth in developing countries, *The European Journal of Development Research*, Vol.20, No.3, pp. 497-506.
- Ram, R. (1985), "Exports and Economic Growth: Some Additional Evidence" *Economic Development and Cultural Change*, Vol. 33: 415-425.
- Shafaeddin, M., Pizarro, J., "From Export Promotion to Import Substitution; Comparative Experience of China and Mexico", University Library of Munich, Germany, 2007, available at <http://mpira.ub.unimuenchen.de/6650/>
- Sengupta, J. K. and J. R. Espana, (1994), Exports and Economic Growth in Asian NICs: an Econometric Analysis for Korea. *Applied Economics* 26: 41-51.
- Shan, J and F. Sun. (1998), On the Export-Led Growth Hypothesis: The Econometric Evidence from China. *Applied Economics*, 30: 1055-1065.
- Zhang, K.H. (2000), "Human Capital, CountrySize, and North-South Manufacturing Multinational Enterprises", *International Economics*, 52 (2), 237-260.
- Zhang, Kevin Honglin. (2001), "Does Foreign Direct Investment Promote Economic growth? Evidence from East Asia and Latin America", *Contemporary Economic Policy*, 19 (2), 175-185.
- World Bank (2011a), Migration and Development Brief 17, Migration and Remittances Unit, Development Economics (DEC) and Poverty Reduction and Economic Management (PREM), World Bank: Washington DC.
- World Bank (2011b), World Development Indicators Online Database, World Bank: Washington DC.

APPENDICES

A1. Data Sources

All the data of the corresponding variables i.e. the real gdp, export and import are collected from the World Bank website that is from the World Development Indicator where the data is spanned from 1980 to 2011

A2. Definition of the Variables

$\ln GDP$ = Ln of Bangladesh Real GDP. The Nominal GDP is deflated by the GDP Deflator.

$\ln X$ = Ln of Bangladesh Export in billion

$\ln M$ = Ln of Bangladesh Import in billion

$\ln FDI$ = Ln of foreign direct investment

$\ln RMT$ = Ln of Remittances in Bangladesh from abroad

Exports of goods and services (% of GDP): Exports of goods and services represent the value of all goods and other market services provided to the rest of the world. They include the value of merchandise, freight, insurance, transport, travel, royalties, license fees, and other services, such as communication, construction, financial, information, business, personal, and government services. They exclude compensation of employees and investment income (formerly called factor services) and transfer payments.

Imports of goods and services (% of GDP): Imports of goods and services represent the value of all goods and other market services received from the rest of the world. They include the value of merchandise, freight, insurance, transport, travel, royalties, license fees, and other services, such as communication, construction, financial, information, business, personal, and government services. They exclude compensation of employees and investment income (formerly called factor services) and transfer payment

Foreign direct investment, net inflows (BoP, current US\$): Foreign direct investment are the net inflows of investment to acquire a lasting management interest (10 percent or more of voting stock) in an enterprise operating in an economy other than that of the investor. It is the sum of equity capital, reinvestment of earnings, other long-term capital, and short-term capital as shown in the balance of payments. This series shows net inflows (new investment inflows less disinvestment) in the reporting economy from foreign investors. Data are in current U.S. dollars

A3. Descriptive Statistics

	<i>LNGDP</i>	<i>LN X</i>	<i>LN M</i>	<i>LN FDI</i>	<i>LN RMT</i>
Mean	1.503987	2.281490	2.862996	17.13716	7.314983
Median	1.599337	2.397895	2.890372	16.43927	7.096276
Maximum	1.902108	3.135494	3.433987	20.73284	9.363061
Minimum	0.587787	1.098612	2.484907	12.42081	5.468060
Std. Dev.	0.337476	0.547860	0.288196	2.641749	1.048521
Skewness	-1.084366	-0.225175	0.325702	-0.056526	0.472400
Kurtosis	3.483718	1.877207	1.964856	1.634271	2.295487
Jarque-Bera	6.583179	1.951304	1.994467	2.503997	1.851979
Probability	0.037195	0.376947	0.368899	0.285933	0.396139
Observations	32	32	32	32	32

